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Scheme 1

Reactions of 2-(Fluoroaryl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehydes with Barbituric and Thiobarbituric Acids

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HCNO and CO can be explained in terms of simple ring fissions⁵.

Fig. 1

PYRIMIDINETRIONES and pyrimidinediones display numerous biological activities¹. 5-Fluorouracil and other pyrimidines are reported to be potent anticancer agents². 5-Allyl-2,4,6-trioxo-5-hexahydropyrimidine- β -sulphooxypropanesulphonic acid displays pronounced antiinflammatory and analgesic activities accompanied by immunosuppressive effect observed in vitro³. 1-(Alkylideneamino)uracils are reported to be useful against weeds in cultivated plants⁴.

As part of our programme for developing new bioactive heterocycles, a number of 5-(2-fluoroaryl-1H-indol-3-ylmethylene)-2,4,6(1H,3H,5H)-pyrimidinetriones/dihydro-5-(2-aryl-1H-indol-3-ylmethylene)-2-thioxo-4,6(1H,5H)-pyrimidinediones (3) were synthesised through condensation of appropriate 2-(fluoroaryl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2) with barbituric/thiobarbituric acid in absolute ethanol. Formylation of appropriate 2-fluoroarylindole (1) with DMF-POCl₃ gave the desired 2-(fluoroaryl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2) (Scheme 1). In the mass spectrum, fragmentation of M⁺ peak of 3a at m/z 349 occurs via two characteristic pathways (a) and (b) (Fig. 1). Simultaneous loss of 2HNCO moieties from the molecular ion is characteristic of barbiturates (pathway-a). In pathway-b loss of

Herbicidal activity : Compounds 3d-f, 3h and 3i were evaluated for their herbicidal activity under submerged and up-land conditions during October-November. Effect of compounds on grass (*Panicum crusgalli*) and annual broad leaved weeds was tested in pre- as well as post-emergence stages under submerged condition at a dosage of 1 and 10 kg/ha. In the up-land condition crops tested were Japanese radish, sugar beet, soyabean germ and the weeds tested were *Polygonum blumei*, *Digitaria adscendens* and *Panicum crusgalli* at a dosage of 10 kg/ha in pre-emergence stage. All the compounds were found to be inactive.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr and ¹⁹F nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer using TMS as internal standard at 89.9 MHz and C₆F₆ as external standard at 84.25 MHz respectively, and mass spectra on Kratos 30 and 50 spectrometers. Elemental analyses were performed by Coleman 29 C, H and N analyser. All the compounds were homogeneous on tlc in various solvent systems.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2a): Phosphorus oxychloride (9.21 ml, 0.06 mol) was added slowly with stirring to *N,N*-dimethylformamide (30 ml) at 10–15°. To the resultant solution, 2-(4-fluorophenyl)indole (10.55 g, 0.05 mol) was added in portions with stirring. The solution was further stirred for 45 min and then poured into water (100 ml). Sodium hydroxide solution (2*N*, 100 ml) was added to it and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1 h. It was cooled, filtered and recrystallised from acetone, (80%). m.p. 270° (Found: C, 75.23; H, 4.04; N, 5.72. $C_{15}H_{10}FNO$ requires: C, 75.31; H, 4.18; N, 5.85%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3140–3220 (br (NH)) and 1625 cm^{-1} (C=O); 1H nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) 9.35 (1H, s, CH), 6.8–7.7 (9H, m, ArH and NH); ^{19}F nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) –104.19 (1F, s, C_6H_4F).

All the other 2-(fluoroaryl)-1*H*-indole-3-carboxaldehydes were prepared similarly.

5-[2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1*H*-indol-3-ylmethylene]-2,4,6-(1*H*, 3*H*, 5*H*)-pyrimidinetrione (3a): A mixture of 2-(4-fluorophenyl)-1*H*-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2.39 g, 0.01 mol) and barbituric acid (1.28 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (50 ml) for about 5 h, whereby the title compound was obtained as orange-red amorphous powder. It was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and recrystallised from dioxan (87%), m.p. 320°d (Found: C, 65.28; H, 3.36; N, 11.90. $C_{19}H_{12}FN_3O_3$ requires: C, 65.32; H, 3.43; N, 12.03%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3100–3240 (NH), 1715 (C=O), 1685 (C=O) and 1630 cm^{-1} (C=O and C=C); 1H nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.15 (2H, br s, both NH of pyrimidine), 8.35 (1H, s, CH) and 7.40–8.00 (9H, m, ArH and NH of indole); ^{19}F nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) –144.19 (1F, s, C_6H_4F); m/z (rel. int.) 349 (M^+) (100) (calcd. for $C_{19}H_{12}FN_3O_3$, 349), pathway-*a*, 263 ($349-C_2H_2N_2O_2$) (22.1), 262 (263-H) (66.2), 234 (262-CO) (40.7), 210 (234- C_2) (12.5), 116 (210- C_6H_5F) (12.15) and 76 (116- CH_2CN) (2.5); pathway-*b*, 278 ($349-C_2HNO_2$) (32.6), 235 (278-HCNO) (30.8), 211 (235- C_2) (14.2), 184 (211-HCN) (5.0) and 94 (184- $C_6H_4CH_2$) (2.5) (Fig. 1).

Compounds 3b–f were prepared similarly (Table 1).

Dihydro-5-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-1*H*-indol-3-ylmethylene]-2-thioxo-4,6-(1*H*, 5*H*)-pyrimidinedione (3g): It was prepared from 2-(4-fluorophenyl)-1*H*-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2.39 g, 0.01 mol) and thiobarbituric acid (1.44 g, 0.01 mol) following similar procedure as described earlier for compound 3a. It was obtained as shiny red crystals (74%), m.p. 290° (Found: C, 62.32; H, 3.14; N, 11.49. $C_{19}H_{12}FN_2O_2S$ requires: C, 62.46; H, 3.28; N, 11.50%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3100–3240 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 1630 (C=O and C=C) and 1290 cm^{-1} (C=S); 1H nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.25 (2H, br s, both NH of pyrimidine), 8.20 (1H, s, CH), 7.25–8.05 (9H, m, ArH and NH of indole); ^{19}F nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) –104.89 (1F, s, C_6H_4F); m/z (rel. int.) 365 (M^+) (100) (calcd. for $C_{19}H_{12}FN_2O_2S$, 365).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3)*

Compd. No.	X	Y	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol formula
3a	4-F	O	320d	87	$C_{15}H_{12}FN_3O_3$
3b	4-F, 3-CH ₃	O	320d	85	$C_{20}H_{14}FN_3O_3$
3c	4-F, 2-Cl	O	290d	89	$C_{16}H_{11}ClFN_3O_3$
3d	4-F, 3-Cl	O	319d	78	$C_{16}H_{11}ClFN_3O_3$
3e	2,5-F ₂	O	300	72	$C_{15}H_{11}F_2N_3O_3$
3f	2,3,4,5,6-F ₅	O	290d	68	$C_{15}H_9F_5N_3O_3$
3g	4-F	S	290	74	$C_{19}H_{12}FN_2O_2S$
3h	4-F, 2-CH ₃	S	281d	72	$C_{20}H_{14}FN_2O_2S$
3i	4-F, 3-CH ₃	S	305d	72	$C_{20}H_{14}FN_2O_2S$
3j	4-F, 2-Cl	S	230d	82	$C_{16}H_{11}ClFN_2O_2S$
3k	4-F, 3-Cl	S	245d	73	$C_{16}H_{11}ClFN_2O_2S$
3l	2,3-F ₂	S	280d	64	$C_{15}H_{11}F_2N_2O_2S$

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Compounds 3h–l were prepared similarly (Table 1).

Acetylation of compound (3a): Compound 3a (1.75 g, 0.005 mol) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (70 ml) for 24 h. The excess acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure and the mixture poured into water. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from alcohol (42%), m.p. 130°d (Found: C, 63.12; H, 3.72; N, 8.81. $C_{25}H_{18}FN_3O_6$ requires: C, 63.15; H, 3.79; N, 8.84%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1715 (C=O and C=O of acetyl), 1685 (C=O) and 1630 cm^{-1} (C=O and C=C); 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.24 (9H, s, 3 × COCH₃), 8.02 (1H, s, CH) and 6.9–7.70 (8H, m, ArH).

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